

IMPROVING THE STATE SUPPORT SYSTEM OF THE COTTON NETWORK

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Abstract. Increasing the economic efficiency of the cotton industry serves, first of all, to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and to ensure food safety. Also, on the other hand, this goal will be achieved through the rational use of the available labor, land, water, material and financial resources of the cotton-growing enterprises, regardless of the forms of ownership, based on the improvement of economic relations between them. The article describes the development of cotton growing in Uzbekistan and the use of new technologies.

Kalit soʻzlar: Cotton fiber, crop rotation, technology, financial investments, investment project, textile industry, technological processes, international experience.

One of the most important issues in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the development of agriculture and the provision of cheap and high-quality products to the population based on it. Due to the importance of this issue, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a law aimed at further development of the farming movement, increasing the efficiency of farm lands and farms, "Protecting the rights and legal interests of farmers, farmers and farm land owners, effective use of agricultural arable land Decree No. PF-5199 dated October 9, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the use system" was adopted.

According to the document, this decree will further support agricultural producers, ensure the efficiency of the use of farmers, peasant farms and homesteads, and ultimately fundamentally change the relationship of landowners to increase their income. adopted for the purpose of change.

Therefore, in the context of the liberalization of the economy and the further acceleration of reforms, increasing the economic efficiency of cotton production and its related activities through the direct and indirect support of the state for the implementation of agrotechnical measures in cotton cultivation is important in the sustainable development of all industries.

Currently, the basis of the agricultural potential of developed countries is the support of agriculture on the basis of various subsidies, subsidies and benefits. In developed countries, the funds spent on agriculture are 1.5-2.0 times more than the market price of the produced products. For example, 30 percent in the USA, 50 percent in Germany, and 75 percent in Japan are subsidies for agricultural products.

In the USA, it has become a tradition to introduce new agrotechnologies every year for the production of high-quality and cheap agricultural products, and this process is supported by the state based on the creation of various preferential mechanisms. In particular, when analyzing the amount of state economic support of a farm for the production of products and the amount of net income received by the year, the state economic support of the cotton industry is the highest - 28, 6,000 dollars, while grain production is 8,700 dollars, and in fruit and vegetable production it is relatively low - 1,900 dollars. 1 The state usually 5 mln. 80 percent of the dollar loan, 5-10 mln. 70 percent up to USD and 10-25 mln. guarantees 60 percent of the loan up to USD. Guaranteed loan terms are 7 years for the purchase of resources, 15 years for machinery and equipment, and 30 years for the purchase or construction of real estate.²

Due to the direct and indirect support of the state to cotton growers in our republic, certain results are being achieved in the development of the sector. The fact that the sector is directly supported from the state budget, that is, financial aid funds are allocated annually from the budget to farms growing cotton in areas with low productivity, and the amount of this fund increases year by year, makes cotton growers financially is gaining a certain importance in preventing the condition from getting worse and in helping them.

Systematization of all the measures implemented in the cotton sector, their interdependence and proportional support should be aimed first of all at the production of raw cotton. The comprehensive support program for cotton raw material growers may include the following directions:

- - to ensure profitable operation of producers of cotton and other products by setting guaranteed purchase prices;
- providing grants and subsidies to producers of raw cotton and improving the financing and insurance system;
- to support the creation of promising varieties and the introduction of seed production systems and new technologies.

¹Farmonov T. Prospects for the development of farms. — T.: "Generation of the new age", 2004.

² Data from the US Department of Agriculture

In our republic, the domestic and foreign cotton market changes depending on demand and supply, market conjuncture. In such conditions, it is necessary for the government to protect the cotton growers from falling prices in the market. When the market price falls below the amount of the accepted costs or the base price, the difference must be paid by the state to the producers.

Although a part of the proceeds from the seeds sold to cotton-growing farms is directed to encourage breeders, it is not enough. Today, it is necessary to accelerate the direct support of the state for the scientific researches being carried out on the creation of a new variety.

The application of new technologies in cotton cultivation will ultimately bring high economic results. However, today, the economic situation of most cotton growers does not allow them to introduce new technologies that require a large amount of money, including mineral fertilizers along with drip and rain irrigation.

New technologies are of great importance in preserving soil and water ecology, as they give high results, and through the direct support of the state, the costs incurred by the state are covered directly and indirectly due to the increase in the amount of production and the saving of the used resources.

It is necessary to introduce special loans for bringing technological equipment to cotton farms, and to give various incentives to banks that provide loans for the same purpose. For this purpose, it would be appropriate to establish a special government fund. Financing the introduction of new technologies on a shared basis will also be beneficial for cotton growers.

Various factors affecting the economic efficiency of agrotechnical activities in the production of cotton raw materials and the problems that need to be solved have a negative impact on the effective operation of farms. This is an obstacle to awakening the interest of farmers in reducing costs and improving the quality of products.

As a result, most of the farms engaged in cotton cultivation are forming as a relatively low-income sector. Therefore, the opportunities to invest in the development of cotton production and to ensure the material benefits of the workers employed in it are decreasing. Because the market demands from the cotton producing farm to exceed the plan, to produce quality products, to make more income, and on this basis, to increase the income of the workers in the farm. At the same time, there are a number of factors that affect the timely and high-quality implementation of agrotechnical activities and do not allow to increase their efficiency.

The existence of situations such as non-effective use of available resources, excessive costs in product production have a negative impact on the efficiency of farm activities. For this purpose, it is appropriate to focus on activities that are of decisive importance in the implementation of the support process, that is, financial and economic activities.

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